

DIGITAL INTEGRATION OF PHYSICS IN STEM EDUCATION IN PEDAGOGICAL UNIVERSITIES IN THE USA AND UKRAINE

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Abstract: The article presents a comparative analysis of the digital integration of physics in STEM education at pedagogical universities in the United States of America and Ukraine. The relevance of the study is due to the need to modernize the training of future physics teachers in the context of digitalization of education and the implementation of STEM-oriented approaches. The purpose of the study is to identify the features and trends of the digital integration of physics in the STEM educational space of pedagogical universities in the United States and Ukraine. It was found that in pedagogical universities in the United States the digital integration of physics in STEM education is systemic in nature and is based on interdisciplinary educational programs, engineering design and problem-based learning. In Ukraine, the integration of physics into STEM education is at the stage of active development and is implemented through the updating of educational programs, the introduction of STEM courses, and the use of digital educational tools. It is concluded that the digital integration of physics into STEM education contributes to the formation of professional and digital competencies of future teachers and requires further methodological and institutional development.

Key words: STEM education, physics, digital integration, pedagogical universities, USA, Ukraine.

Legislative changes and systemic support for STEM in the United States in 2014–2015, with the adoption by the US Congress of the STEM Education Act, which expanded the official definition of STEM to include computer science and provided support for large-scale programs in the field of STEM education, led to the

formation of a single infrastructure for supporting STEM at all levels of education (K–12, secondary and higher education), including teacher training, cooperation between universities and businesses [1]. As a pedagogical discipline, physics has become one of the leading areas for the implementation of digital technologies. US educational institutions have begun to integrate digital simulations, virtual laboratories and software into physics courses as part of STEM education, which has made it possible to shift the emphasis from isolated study of subjects to interdisciplinary projects and research. In the Ukrainian education system, the integration of STEM appeared much later mainly within the framework of reforms and the introduction of innovative pedagogical practices. A key event was the adoption of the Concept for the Development of Science and Mathematics Education (STEM Education) in 2020, which for the first time systematically outlined the strategic directions of STEM at all levels of education, including content, methods, and competencies for the 21st century. Although STEM did not become part of formal legislation in Ukraine as early as in the United States, domestic higher education institutions gradually began to introduce interdisciplinary approaches, digital tools, and project activities into curricula, including physics. These changes have accelerated in the context of the global digitalization of education [4] and the requirements for digital literacy of future teachers, which is reflected in practical scientific research on the application of digital technologies in STEM education.

The purpose of the study is to conduct a comparative analysis of the digital integration of physics into STEM education at pedagogical universities in the United States and Ukraine, as well as to identify promising areas for improving the training of future physics teachers in the context of digitalization of education.

STEM education in Higher Education Institutions of the USA training is often carried out through specialized undergraduate programs with the integration of pedagogical and STEM components (for example, Physics with Teaching Major or Physics Education). These programs include courses in modern teaching methods, the use of ICT in the classroom, STEM-integrated lesson design and technology in physics. There are also special STEM teacher training programs, such as UTeach (at

selected universities), which form competencies in STEM teaching methods in an integrated context. In the USA, digital educational resources that support the study of physics and STEM are widely used: PhET Interactive Simulations is known an interactive online simulation to explain physical phenomena; National Science Digital Library (NSDL) is known a digital library of STEM resources for teachers and students. Platforms such as PhysPort help teachers apply research methods and digital tools in teaching physics. These resources not only serve as content, but also form skills in using digital technologies in pedagogical practice. National STEM initiatives in physics and professional teacher training in the USA are implemented through a number of professional development programs. QuarkNet is a national US program for science teachers with a focus on high-energy physics, funded by NSF and the Department of Energy. The program unites more than 50 centers across the country (universities + national laboratories), where teachers gain experience in participating in real physics research, master data and methods, and integrate this knowledge into STEM classroom practice. Teachers analyze measurements, work with data from collaborations, develop project tasks and present them to students, which promotes the connection between university physics and STEM education in school. Among the most frequently used digital simulations in physics teaching, the most «successful» is PhET Interactive Simulations. The PhET project (University of Colorado, Boulder) provides free interactive simulations in physics, chemistry, mathematics, and more, which are widely used in university physics courses and STEM projects. The simulations support the visualization of abstract physical concepts (e.g., Newton's laws, electromagnetic phenomena) and can be integrated as part of laboratory, project, and interdisciplinary activities. PhET simulations are successfully used in the training of students and future teachers, forming STEM competencies through digital modeling and experimentation.

An important point is the support for research-based physics teaching practices. PhysPort is a central platform for physics professionals that offers teaching methods, assessments, digital resources, and learning modules based on Physics Education Research. As of the end of 2025, $\approx 47\%$ of US physics departments are confirmed as

active users of the resource, which indicates a widespread practice of implementing research-oriented STEM methodologies into curricula. The role of university programs and teachers in STEM integration of physics is most clearly represented by the Learning Assistant Program (University of Colorado Boulder), where student assistants participate in teaching physics, helping to implement a research-oriented approach and STEM projects in college classrooms. This is a model that strengthens the connection between physics disciplines, pedagogical practice, and STEM competencies of future teachers. PhysTEC is the association for physics teacher education, which unites universities and colleges in the United States to improve the quality of physics and physical science teacher education in the context of STEM education. It supports the development of programs, trainings and communities of practice for future teachers aimed at integrating physics with technology and pedagogical scientific approaches.

The experience of QuarkNet and PhET shows that thousands of physics teachers in schools and universities are trained through QuarkNet and apply the acquired skills in STEM courses. PhET simulations are used in practice in physics laboratories, lectures and STEM projects at dozens of universities in the United States (for example, in Boulder, Kansas, Maryland, etc.). Many physics teacher education programs include courses in digital technologies, modeling and interdisciplinary STEM projects (through PhysTec, PhysPort, Learning Assistant Program). The integration of digital tools (simulations, QuarkNet research, PhysPort resources) allows to increase motivation and understanding of physical concepts by future teachers; to form STEM competencies (digital, analytical, experimental); to build interdisciplinary educational trajectories (physics + engineering + technology); which meets the modern requirements for training STEM teachers in the USA.

Digital integration of physics into STEM in Ukraine depends on the training of future physics teachers. In Ukraine, the training of STEM teachers, including physics, is not always structured as a separate STEM specialty (unlike in the USA). More often, future teachers receive training within the framework of general physical or natural education, and not through separate programs that integrate STEM subjects

together with digital methods [2], [3]. However, research emphasizes the need to introduce digital technologies and STEM methods into the training of future physics teachers, in particular ICT tools, simulations, project technologies and cloud services, digital tools (simulations, BYOD/cloud services, Arduino projects, etc.) as means to increase student motivation; organization of blended learning; combination of traditional experiment with digital laboratories. These approaches form the information and digital competence of future teachers, which is a component of effective STEM teaching. Using the Arduino platform in the training of physics teachers for STEM-oriented teaching in universities allows students to learn to implement their projects - from simple physical experiments to group tasks, which contributes to the development of practical skills, critical thinking and technological literacy in teacher training.

Research shows that blended learning standards in physics include STEM-oriented technologies, digital laboratory facilities, mobile devices and BYOD (Bring Your Own Device) approach for implementing physical experiments with STEM components. This means that physics is not studied in isolation, but is combined with digital tools, project activities and interdisciplinary approaches, which is characteristic of STEM education.

Pedagogical research notes the interdisciplinary application of STEM approaches in teaching physics, when physical problems are solved in the context of technology, engineering and mathematics, which contributes to the formation of professional competencies of future teachers. This approach is aimed at developing key skills of the 21st century (critical thinking, collaboration, project work) in combination with subject knowledge. Physical experiment in the STEM educational environment is associated with the use of innovative technologies, digital devices and integrated methodologies, which not only enhances the understanding of physical phenomena, but also forms STEM competencies. This is concrete evidence that physics is included in STEM education not only as a separate subject, but as part of a comprehensive educational process, where experimental skills are combined with technologies. Practical integration of physics into STEM education, namely project

activities with Arduino for students of pedagogical profile is used to implement real physical experiments in a STEM context. Blended digital learning and BYOD for physics laboratories are used in university courses to combine theory with digital experimentation. Interdisciplinary courses Physics + Tech + Pedagogy are aimed at forming STEM competencies of future teachers. These are examples of the implementation of STEM education in physics at Ukrainian universities, which demonstrate that physics is not only taught as a traditional discipline, but is also included in modern STEM initiatives that form the professional competencies of future teachers.

Digital integration of physics is a key component of effective STEM education in pedagogical universities. The experience of the USA demonstrates the effectiveness of a systematic approach to training STEM teachers with the extensive use of digital technologies. In the USA, physics is integrated into STEM training through national programs, digital resources and pedagogical innovations (QuarkNet, PhET, PhysPort, PhysTEC). Physics is not an isolated discipline, but part of the STEM environment, where digital simulations and research are used in pedagogical programs. Systemic support for the training of physics teachers and STEM competencies contributes to improving the quality of education and professional readiness of future teachers for modern schools. In Ukraine, the digital integration of physics into STEM education is at the stage of development and requires further regulatory and methodological support. Promising directions are the modernization of educational programs, the introduction of interdisciplinary STEM courses and the development of digital competencies of future physics teachers. Adapting US best practices, taking into account the national educational context, will contribute to improving the quality of teacher education in Ukraine.

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